

UNDERSTANDING CAUSES & REMEDIES OF LOW PROFITABILITY OF CLOUD TECHNOLOGY MANAGED SERVICE DELIVERY PROJECTS IN INDUSTRY 4.0 ERA

Bhavna Agarwal

Himanshu Agarwal

Parvez Talib

Abstract:

To measure is to know. Adequate quantitative measurements are available to know the status of profitability of the projects. Based on these quantitative measurements, in case it is found that a project has recorded less than expected profitability, then it becomes necessary to deep dive and carry out a thorough root cause analysis with the help of indepth qualitative study. Accordingly the present study is focused on studying and providing understanding of various qualitative aspects associated with profitability of Cloud Technology managed service delivery projects operating in Industry 4.0 scenerio. This study focus at addressing the scope of improvement in an optimum manner and preventing recurrence of the problem with the aim of achieving & maintaining targeted profitability at the project management level. Successful achievement of these objectives depends on the extent of strategic implementation of findings of this study by the concerned project leadership teams.

Key Words:

Industry 4.0, Cloud Technology, Profitability, Financial, Projects, Managed Service Provider

Introduction

Peter Drucker has given the golden words of wisdom, “What is measured, gets managed and improved.” Method of measuring quantitative profitability for establishing past performance records of the business units already exists. Putting it in very simple words profitability is surplus of Revenue over Costs, expressed as a percentage e.g. **Gross Margin = (Revenue – Costs) / Revenue.**

Profitability is a very significant metrics to track, monitor and assess the success or failure of a business unit. This metric also enables the meaningful quantitative comparison among multiple business units operating in the same industry, and across different industries also, if required. The area of interest in this study are the factors associated with this metrics, specifically the cases of low profitability of Cloud Technology Managed Service Delivery Projects during current Industry 4.0 era.

The quantitative profitability metrics invokes qualitative study in detail to identify causes associated with low profitability and potential areas of improvement / remedies. Understanding of these causes & remedies will enable practicing Project Managers of Cloud Technology managed service delivery projects to identify, address and remove the underlying root cause impeding their project profitability, at the same time creating a knowledge repository for future managers to rely upon and avoid pitfalls

wherever an analogy with this study can be drawn.

Overview of Industry 4.0, Cloud Technology and its Service Providers

In the present day’s significant transformation era, industries are relying heavily on interconnectivity, automation, machine learning and real time data processing for conjunction of physical production and digital technologies. This transition is known as Industry 4.0 i.e. the fourth revolution in industries, a new approach overhauling end-to-end business operations and growth. A German government memo released in 2013 brought up the discussion about “Industrie 4.0”. This high-tech strategy document outlined a plan to almost fully computerize the manufacturing industry without the need for human involvement (plattform-i40, 2019). With the onset of Industry 4.0, more and more production units are raising demand for sharing data across their sites and geographical boundaries.

This is an ideal stage for Cloud Technology to flourish, which provides reduced reaction time (up to milliseconds) for its customers while at the same time offering huge potentials of harvesting profits for its service providers. As a result, both the parties i.e. customer as well as service provider will increasingly be interested in leveraging Cloud Technology for enabling swift and flawless production. Cloud Technology is a new paradigm for hosting and delivering

services over the Internet, the practice of using interconnected remote servers hosted on the internet to store, manage and process information. The National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) defines Cloud Technology as “a model for enabling ubiquitous, convenient, on-demand network access to a shared pool of configurable computing resources (e.g. networks, servers, storage, applications and services) that can be rapidly provisioned and released with minimal management effort or service provider interaction.” (Technology, 2011). Cloud Technology has changed the landscape of Information Technology (IT).

When a business invests in Cloud Technology, such business is not required to maintain huge in-house IT Team of its own, instead such business gets benefited by the regular updates and maintenance performed by the Managed Service Providers (MSPs) of Cloud Technology services. MSPs are information technology services providers who manage and assume responsibility for providing a defined set of services for their clients. These MSPs manage cloud platforms and lease resources to serve the end users according to a usage-based pricing model. Profitability of individual projects being operated by these Cloud Technology MSPs is area of interest in this study.

Research Objective

Following are the objectives of this study with reference to Cloud Technology Managed Service Delivery projects operating in Industry 4.0 era:

1. To identify the causes leading to quantitatively low profitability.
2. To support and mentor their Project Managers for preventing recurring failure in reducing costs, optimizing revenue and in achieving their targeted profitability.
3. To support and mentor their Project Managers for achieving consistent success in maintaining high profitability at project level so that a decent Net Profit is recorded at the overall organization level.
4. To shift the focus of their Project Managers from a reactive to proactive management of profitability.

Literature Review

Cloud Technology being a promising avenue, rich literature is available exploring various aspects of it. Scholars across the world are continuously adding to it and opening newer research avenues also, contributing towards this knowledge area. The subjects dealt with in the papers published in reputed peer reviewed journals and those presented in various conferences, evidence that studies have been done to track and analyze the evaluation of Cloud Technology (Srivastava & Khan, 2018), business opportunities and business values for application of this technology (Leimeister,

Böhm, Riedl, & Krcmar, 2010) for example: hosting accounting softwares (Awad, 2011) and similar model to be replicated in other departments of business organizations. On a wider level, application of Cloud Technology for enabling supply chain integration with Industry 4.0 (Ardito, Petruzzelli, Panniello, & Achille, 2019) (Shee, Shah, Fairfield, & Pujawan, 2018) and potential of Cloud Technology to strengthen the objectives of Industry 4.0 (Oztemel & Samet, 2018) have been analyzed. For service industry as well, utilization of cloud based services in e-governance (Joshi, Islam, & Islam, 2017) (Umar, Mehmood, Majeed, & Muham, 2019) has been explored. From implementation perspective, scholars have attempted to identify innovation dynamics, determinants and guidelines of Cloud Computing adoption, diffusion and usage (El-Haddadeh, 2019) (Bidgoli, 2018) (Sabi, Uzoka, Langmia, Njeh, & Tsuma, 2018) (Low, Chen, & Wu, 2011). Researchers have also deliberated upon Cloud service models & its implications such as security, reliability, privacy etc. (Prasad, Naik, & Bapuji, 2013) (Padhy, Patra, & Satapathy, 2011), paying due attention towards concept of Cloud Architecture (Kumar & Goudar, 2012), surveying the state-of-the-art of cloud computing, architecture, design challenges (Zhang, Cheng, & Boutaba, 2010) including server failures and hardware repairs for large datacenters (Vishwanath & Nagappan, 2010).

The para above provides insight about technical aspects of Cloud Technology being explored. In addition to it, studies have been done to evaluate Cloud Technology from Financial perspective, its relationship and contribution towards business strategy (Emerald, 2019) (Ross & Blumenstein, 2013). Researchers have continuously explored the cost benefit analysis model to help customer for taking call to adopt or not to adopt Cloud Technology (Nanath & Pillai, 2013), costs incurred by customers of cloud services and charging/pricing model adopted by service providers (Kumar & Goudar, 2012). Return On Investments (ROI) model for Cloud Technology customers, including the valuation of benefits associated with this technology (Mangiuc, 2017) (Misra & Mondal, 2011) has grabbed the attention of scholars time and again. Considerable work has already been done by the scholars and much more is getting added to the knowledge repository with each passing day.

Research Gaps

Based on the Literature Review undertaken by this researcher about Cloud Technology, it appears that:

1. Most of the studies are focused on the technological aspects, service delivery, application areas, operational performance indicators e.g. Data Centre Services, and a few studies are done on the financial aspects related to Cloud Technology.
2. The studies which have dealt with financial aspects, these studies are

focused on business value, costs incurred, investments done and ROI received by the customers availing Cloud Technology managed services to run their businesses. These studies are not adequately evaluating the financial aspects of projects being operated by MSPs of Cloud Technology.

3. The studies which have dealt with the financial aspects of projects being operated by MSPs of Cloud Technology, these are limited to study of charging/pricing models adopted by them.

Area of profitability achieved by Cloud Technology MSPs seems still pending to be explored. Thus this present study attempts to understand their profitability at their individual project level, specifically focusing on causes along with the corresponding remedies for low Profitability.

Research Methodology

Based on the existing gaps indicated by the extensive Literature Review conducted and presented in the Para 4 of this study, researcher was motivated to undertake this study.

This being a **Qualitative** research, **Explanatory Case Study Method** has been adopted to carry out this in-depth detailed study in real-life context, because this intricately designed methodology reveals a comprehensive and complete presentation of facts, as they have

occurred earlier, providing secondary database by way of primary recounting by those involved in the occurrence (Chawla & Sondhi, 2011).

Population for this study is formed by Cloud Technology managed service delivery projects. Cloud Technology being a new area of operations in Industry 4.0 era and profitability (specifically low Gross Margin) being a sensitive & confidential metrics of measurement, **Sampling** from this population is done by using **Snowballing Design** (Chawla & Sondhi, 2011) and a small number of such projects has been worked with as **Sampling Units** for this study.

Findings have been worked out based on analysis conducted during this study.

Data Collection and Analysis

Researcher adopted a multi-modal approach of Case Study Methodology, collecting data from different sources i.e. reviewing documents/archived records, exploring the project artifacts and detailed face-to-face discussions with the project leadership teams, so that the research objectives may be explored adequately. Data collected for this study belongs to calendar years 2016 and 2017. During the data tabulation process, Projects' names were coded with alphabets. Researcher collected Revenue and Cost data of projects being studied and performed holistic quantitative analysis on this data to establish the past financial performance of these projects. In this process,

researcher calculated gross margin for each month and average of three & six months. In these results, there were many instances of spikes, therefore Average Gross Margin of nine (9) months was calculated in order to iron out spikes appearing in short duration data due to various reasons e.g. seasonal effects,

project start-up / wind-up, contingent and unforeseen reasons etc. These metrics helped in understanding past financial profitability and a reasonable prediction for future performance. The quantitative conclusions thus obtained about nine (9) months Gross Margin (%) data is presented below:

Project Code	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O
Actual Gross Margin (9 months %)	38	48	43	30	32	43	36	36	42	26	0	23	30	36	30
Targeted Gross Margin %	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50
Difference (Actual - Targeted)	-12	-2	-7	-20	-18	-7	-14	-14	-8	-24	-50	-27	-20	-14	-20

Table 1; Source – Self compiled

This quantitative analysis clearly shows that the quarter wise Actual Gross Margin achieved by these sampling units is lower than their Targeted Gross Margin. Quantum of this variation differs among various projects as shown by the table above. In order to maintain the equality, projects with the same targeted profit (i.e.50%) have been included in the sampling units.

Once these Profitability metrics were calculated in quantitative terms, researcher applied “5 Why” method to peel away through the layers of symptoms, to identify the root cause of low profitability and to reveal causal factors associated with the quantitative status of profitability. For this purpose, researcher had

interactive sessions with the Project Leadership teams of sampling units, wherein researcher has recorded various anecdotes, comments and illustrations as vital pieces of qualitative information. At this stage researcher also motivated the Project Leadership Teams to brainstorm about solutions/remedies available to them for improving the profitability and for achieving financial targets set for their projects. Researcher crosschecked the facts/discrepancies with in the data collected, utilizing qualitative data to corroborate & support the quantitative data and vice-versa, identifying the patterns in the data. Based upon this analysis, researcher described under seven Categories, these patterns emerging

among causes of low profitability, as presented below:

1. Customer contract specific causes
2. Delayed collection from customers
3. Incorrect billing to customer
4. Manpower costs
5. Incorrect allocation / apportionment of costs & revenue
6. Onsite deployment costs
7. Travel & Transport costs

Detailed description of each of these categories is presented in Appendix – I.

The entire quantitative and qualitative data collected from the sampling units, was analyzed thoroughly to find its connect with the research objectives as described above, ultimately reaching out to the solution to address the problems. In general, the majority of the respondents perceived that the causes identified in this study contribute towards challenge of meeting their profitability targets. Finally the study arrived at actionable findings which are useful for decision making and improving project profitability.

Findings

It is extremely important for any project to be competitive and remain proactive in Industry 4.0 environment and for this, the Project Managers have to be dynamic, constantly taking and aligning their decisions, accelerating changes in business processes with an objective to optimize the project profitability. These practicing managers need guidance points

to assist them in such logical decision making. Having traverse through the data collected, analysis done and discussions held with various Project Leadership Teams, this study identified the causes of low profitability (listed in Appendix I) in the area of interest and develops the Project Managers' understanding to implement the logical decision which shall be helpful in reducing costs and enhancing profitability of Cloud Technology managed service delivery projects.

Improving profitability is not an easy task, it involves bold steps of reduction in cost along with increase in revenue for improving the bottom line and remaining proactively vigilant about the same. Findings of this study are presented herein-below as a candid feedback for the benefit of Cloud Technology Managed Service Delivery Project Managers through its strategic implementation:

1. **Prepare** Action plan to address the identified issues and areas of improvement
2. **Review** the action plan along with key stakeholders of the project (including customers/business partners), taking into account all relevant factors
3. **Finalize** the action plan, **implement** the same and **monitor** its post-implementation progress continuously
4. **Self-Review** the Revenue, Cost and Gross Margin data on monthly basis, analyzing the spikes objectively.
5. **Peer Reviews** covering the factors highlighted in this study is necessary.

In this process, each Project Manager needs to review a project other than his own and to submit the review report to their Strategic Business Unit Leadership team.

6. **Causal analysis** must be done in case of below average performances recorded.
7. **Best practices** must be shared by the projects who have consistently exceeded their targets / benchmarks.
8. Adherence to the following **operational aspects** is prominently highlighted:
 - 8.1 **Customer contract** must be signed in timely manner and on realistic grounds, paying due attention towards service volumes, service charges, discounts and other benefits. At the same time, Project Leadership Teams are advised to improvise on their commercial prowess for keeping pace with the stringent budget, lean team and completion of work assignments with each passing year.
 - 8.2 Project team is advised to get actively involved in **3 way reconciliation** among customers' records, own invoices raised and realization of payments from customers, on timely & periodic basis and to remain constantly vigilant for the same so that Month-on-Month GM of the project may present consistent picture:

- a) Ensure that **timely billing** is done to the customer for all services provided during the corresponding period
- b) Track the **Resource Units** (Volume Inventory) on monthly basis, making the RU counts fetching process robust & transparent and get the RUs minutely **verified** from independent expert to ensure its correctness
- c) Ensure that **payments are received** from the customer as per agreed terms and the same must be reconciled on monthly basis
- d) Improve collections and **avoid Bad Debts** provisions
- e) Distribute the Revenue/cost in such a manner which does not result in skewed distribution across Project locations/segments
- f) **Discrepancies**, if any, and process to remove it should be defined scientifically so that the records give true picture and anomaly is not carried over to future periods.
- g) Execute **concrete Margin Improvement Plan** and improve Gross Margin Quarter-On-Quarter
- h) In genuine cases of low profitability, maintain atleast the current rate of Gross Margins, if not able to improve upwards

8.3 **Optimize manpower**, drawing delicate balance between improved financials and qualitative service delivery, using methods like:

- a) Keep only eligible and requisite employees on roll
- b) Cross-skill the employees
- c) Reduce Non-billable employees count
- d) Offer On-call support to customer
- e) Release/replace/move upwards the high cost senior resources
- f) Replace high cost on-site local hires with own employees
- g) In case (e) above is infeasible, take these employees on own roll to save the commission cost being paid to their recruitment agency
- h) Maintain pool of visa ready employees for onsite customer locations
- i) Tap the network around to identify suitable resources
- j) Maintain pool of trained junior resource and to present them to the customer in a planned manner during ramp down activity
- k) Utilize monthly Volumetric analysis to identify the low performers and cut down on low performers by applying load balancing

l) Monitor Per Person Revenue also

m) Be vigilant about opportunities for increasing billable manpower with robust provisions to control billing leakage

n) Focus on automation and on becoming more efficient, disrupting constructively, in order to remain competitive by releasing manpower

8.4 Avail **benefit of Offshore leverage** without adversely impacting End User activities and taking customer into confidence for such arrangement. Project can start with giving parallel service from offshore without hampering deliverables, and switch to offshore completely, once customer's confidence is gained on seamless services from offshore.

8.5 Take calculated risk in implementing **cost management measures** which are tough in nature and may appear difficult to the lower staff members:

a) Optimize the domestic and international travel cost

b) Optimize the local transport cost incurred for employees

c) Avail possibility of getting project investment reimbursed from the customer

d) Be very vigilant during verification of bills which

lead to the booking of cost in project's cost sheet

- 8.6 Keep on highlighting to senior leadership team about additional business opportunities & regarding negotiating additional revenue for additional work

This study clearly found that increase / decrease in business scope does not form part of profitability improvement plan. Profitability can be increased by better cost management & increased revenue and the same can be maintained by staying proactively vigilant about it, without becoming complacent based on profitability targets achieved for a short duration or intermittently.

Conclusion

The 1st objective of this study was to identify the causes leading to quantitatively low profitability in Cloud Technology Managed Service Delivery projects operating in Industry 4.0 era. Thorough discussions with sampling units, as part of qualitative study, researcher has achieved this objective and a detailed description of such causes, broadly classified under 7 categories, has been presented in Appendix – I.

2nd and 3rd objectives of this study were set to mentor Project Managers of Cloud Technology MSPs for controlling costs, optimizing revenue, achieving their targeted profits and maintain the same in a consistent manner. Discussions, deliberations and analysis during this

study, urged these Project Managers to review the state of their affairs from all of these angles and after identifying causes as per Appendix – I, they were also able to work upon corresponding remedies which is the take away of this study, to be applied in practical scenarios as per the applicability.

With reference to the 4th objective of this study, researcher has drawn the attention of subject Project Managers to such financial aspects of their project management practice, which were somehow getting overlooked amidst of routine service delivery jobs. This study helps Cloud Technology managed service delivery projects to identify the areas having scope of improvement in their respective projects scenario and to focus their proactive attention on the same, ultimately resulting into better profitability, thus providing remedies to them.

The main conclusion from the above is the Cloud Technology Managed Service Delivery Project Managers can shift their focus from a reactive to proactive management of their project profitability by keeping a tab on causes identified and remedies advised through this study. This researcher encourages strategic implementation of the findings of this study so that multiple objectives of individual project profitability, net profitability of the organizations and GDP targets of the whole nation in this Industry 4.0 era may be achieved in a sustainable manner.

This study has also contributed towards knowledge repository which helps practicing managers at large, to quickly pick up and apply required improvement suggestion applicable to their project scenario while at the same time focusing due part of their attention on technical service delivery aspects. Cloud Technology being the latest technology, this study will help finance professionals also to guide their clients in this field, with specific reference to the following:

1. Tangible financial benefits
2. Optimization of manpower
3. Cost Management, Saving and Avoidance
4. Realization of incremental revenue
5. Enhanced profitability
6. Awareness towards customer contract clauses

Recommendations for Further Studies and Research

To the best of the researchers' knowledge, there have been no other studies done relating to causes and remedies of low profitability of Cloud Technology Managed Service Delivery projects. Through this study, researchers have expended the boundaries of theoretical as well as practical knowledge, opening new vistas to be deliberated upon as the previous studies were primarily regarding technical aspects of Cloud Technology and ROI for its customers. Based on the conclusions presented in this study, researchers suggest that future research should be undertaken on the competency,

ability and willingness of Project Leadership Teams to manage and own the financial aspects of their projects with specific reference to the scenario where core competency of such leadership teams is Information Technology.

References

- Ardito, L., Petruzzelli, A. M., Panniello, U., & Achille, C. (2019). Towards Industry 4.0. *Business Process Management Journal*, Bradford Vol. 25, Iss. 2, pp: 323-346.
- Awad, R. (2011). Considerations on Cloud Computing for CPAs. *The CPA Journal*, New York Vol. 81, Iss. 9, Sep pp: 11-12.
- Bidgoli, H. (2018). Cloud Computing Deployment: What Have We Learned from Real Life Implementations and Practices. *Journal of Strategic Innovation and Sustainability*, West Palm Beach Vol. 13, Iss. 1, Jul pp 36-52.
- Chawla, D., & Sondhi, N. (2011). *Research Methodology - Concepts and Cases*. New Delhi: Vikas Publishing House Private Limited.
- El-Haddadeh, R. (2019). Digital Innovation Dynamics Influence on Organisational Adoption: The Case of Cloud Computing Services. *Information Systems Frontiers*, New York, Apr, pp: 1-15.
- Emerald. (2019). The relationship between cloud adoption and business strategy.

- Strategic Direction*, Bradford Vol. 35, Iss. 4, pp: 7-9.
- Joshi, P. R., Islam, S., & Islam, S. (2017). A Framework for Cloud Based E-Government from the Perspective of Developing Countries. *Future Internet*, Basel Vol. 9, Iss. 4, pp: 80.
- Kumar, S., & Goudar, R. H. (2012). Cloud Computing – Research Issues, Challenges, Architecture, Platforms and Applications: A Survey. *International Journal of Future Computer and Communication*, Vol. 1, No. 4, December, pp.356-360.
- Leimeister, S., Böhm, M., Riedl, C., & Krcmar, H. (2010). The Business Perspective of Cloud Computing: Actors, Roles and Value Networks. *European Conference on Information Systems* (p. 56). AIS Electronic Library (AISeL).
- Low, C., Chen, Y., & Wu, M. (2011). Understanding the determinants of cloud computing adoption. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, Vol. 111 No. 7, pp. 1006-1023.
- Mangiuc, D. (2017). Accountants and the cloud – Involving the professionals. *Accounting and Management Information Systems*, Bucharest Vol. 16, Iss. 1, pp: 179-198.
- Misra, S. C., & Mondal, A. (2011). Identification of a company's suitability for the adoption of cloud computing and modelling its corresponding Return on Investment. *Mathematical and Computer Modelling*, Feb. Vol. 53, pp. 504-21.
- Nanath, K., & Pillai, R. (2013). A Model for Cost-Benefit Analysis of Cloud Computing. *Journal of International Technology and Information Management*, San Bernadino Vol. 22, Iss. 3, pp: 95-II.
- Oztemel, E., & Samet, G. (2018). Literature review of Industry 4.0 and related technologies. *Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing*, London (Jul) pp: 1-56.
- Padhy, R. P., Patra, M. R., & Satapathy, S. C. (2011). Cloud Computing: Security Issues and Research Challenges. *IRACST - International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technology & Security (IJCSITS)*, Vol. 1, No. 2, December, pp. 136 - 146.
- plattform-i40*. (2019, April 04). Retrieved from start page / About the platform / Workgroups / Technology and application scenarios: <https://www.plattformi40.de/PI40/Redaktion/DE/Standardartikel/arbeitsgruppe-02.html>
- Prasad, M., Naik, R. L., & Bapuji, V. (2013). Cloud Computing : Research Issues and Implications. *Institute of Advanced Engineering and Science* *www.iaesjInternational Journal of Cloud Computing and Services Science (IJ-CLOSER)* , ISSN: 2089-3337, Vol.2, No.2, April, pp. 134~140.
- Ross, P., & Blumenstein, M. (2013). Cloud computing: the nexus of strategy and technology. *The Journal of Business*

- Strategy*, Boston Vol. 34, Iss. 4, pp: 39-47.
- Sabi, H. M., Uzoka, F.-M. E., Langmia, K., Njeh, F. N., & Tsuma, C. K. (2018). A cross-country model of contextual factors impacting cloud computing adoption at universities in sub-Saharan Africa. *Information Systems Frontiers*, New York Vol. 20, Iss. 6, Dec, pp: 1381-1404.
- Shee, H., Shah, J. M., Fairfield, L., & Pujawan, N. (2018). The impact of cloudenabled process integration on supply chain performance and firm sustainability: the moderating role of top management. *Supply Chain Management*, Bradford Vol. 23, Iss. 6, pp. 500-517.
- Srivastava, P., & Khan, R. (2018). A Review Paper on Cloud Computing. *International Journals of Advanced Research in Computer Science and Software Engineering*, ISSN: 2277-128X (Volume-8, Issue-6) pp. 17-20.
- Technology, N. I. (2011, October 25). *Final Version of NIST Cloud Computing Definition Published*. Retrieved from <https://www.nist.gov/news-events/news/2011/10/final-version-nist-cloud-computing-definition-published>
- Umar, A., Mehmood, A., Majeed, M. F., & Muham, S. (2019). Innovative Citizen's Services through Public Cloud in Pakistan: User's Privacy Concerns and Impacts on Adoption. *Mobile Networks and Applications*, New York Vol. 24, Iss. 1, Feb pp: 47-68.
- Vishwanath, K. V., & Nagappan, N. (2010). Characterizing cloud computing hardware reliability. *Proceeding SoCC '10 Proceedings of the 1st ACM symposium on Cloud computing* (pp. 193-204). Indianapolis, Indiana, USA: ACM New York, NY, USA ©2010.
- Zhang, Q., Cheng, L., & Boutaba, R. (2010). Cloud computing: state-of-the-art and research challenges. *Journal of Internet Services and Applications*, May, Volume 1, Issue 1, pp 7-18.

Appendix – I: Causes of Low Profitability

S. No.	Categories	Root Causes of Low Profitability
1.	Customer Contract	Project unable to raise invoice & realize revenue due to: 1. delay in finalization of contract with customer 2. bill rate under revision
2.		Project accepted the low bill rates / revenue because of primary objective being to enter into a particular market segment/geography
3.		Project accepted additional work order in the existing contract at reduced bill rates
4.		Reduction in bill rates at the time of renewal of customer contract for the same scope & volume of work
5.		Project gave Volumetric Discount to the customer
6.		Year-On-Year Efficiency clause quantum remaining the same inspite of the reduced bill rates in additional work scope / renewed contract
7.		Year-On-Year productivity gain passed on to the customer while scope of work remaining the same
8.		Reduction in service volumes / scope of work
9.		Quarter-on-Quarter Reduction in revenue leading to reducing trend in actual GM
10.		Extremely low / negative Gross Margin of one / few segments of the project has caused aggregate Gross margin of the project to remain low
11.		Project decides not to bill certain components of costs to the customer in order to maintain customer relationship
12.		Strict data security requirements not allowing Offshoring of services
13.		Higher count of manpower to be deployed due to 24*7 service availability mandated by the contract, even though the service volume is low
14.		Reduction in billable manpower as mandated by customer contract hence Project not able to bill for all the manpower deployed, inspite of work volume / efforts involved remaining the same
15.		Ambiguity in contract regarding procedure and methodology of billing, resulting in disputed billing
16.	Delayed collection from Customers	Frequent delays in the payments received from the customer resulting in Bad Debt Provisions
17.		Project did not follow up for the old receivables pending from the customer
18.		Project has not done Reconciliation between billing done and

		payment received from customer and incorrect & unreconciled accounts were carried forward for a very long time, making it difficult to track pending collections from the customer
19.		Project adopted an unscientific and adhoc style to reconcile accounts and improper treatment of differences found during reconciliation
20.	Improper Billing to Customer	Inconsistent revenue and Gross Margin due to: 1. accumulated / carry forward / delayed / over billing from previous accounting period 2. adjustments of previous billing errors 3. credit / debit Notes settled after unduly long time gap
21.		Incorrect billing done to customer due to: 1. a portion of billable services not included in the bill 2. volumetric details (forming basis of billing) are not calculated correctly 3. bill rates revised upwards still billing done with previous lower rates 4. undue credit note extended to the customer 5. computerised system of billing not followed, making it difficult to track pending billing
22.	Manpower Costs	Adequate controls not exercised on eligibility of people taken on roll of the project
23.		Budgeted manpower as well as service volumes being Underestimated
24.		Project did not claim corresponding increase in revenue when manpower was increased inspite of billing being based on Headcount
25.		Increase in manpower deployed due to increased service volumes, without any proportionate increase in revenue
26.		Manpower deployed in Governance and non-billable positions not yielding revenue
27.		FERLO impact
28.		Additional manpower due to attrition / replacement and additional work expected, adding to cost
29.		Due to high service volumes, Project unable to reduce its manpower inspite of reduction in bill rates
30.		Existing employee replaced by the employee of higher grade, thus increasing the project cost while revenue remains the same
31.		Projects do not plan to manage the expected rise in cost due to foreseeable promotions of team members

32.		Project not able to realign/replace the team member due to customer being sensitive about change in resources
33.		Non-availability of manpower possessing requisite skill set, hence Project compelled to take expensive local hire at on-site customer location
34.		Cloud technology being new, Projects are still in the process of understanding it. After understanding the technology and migration towards it, they will be able to release the resources and reduce costs
35.		Additional allowances being paid as per nature of job e.g. Night Shift Allowance
36.		High proportion of senior staff, incurring huge costs
37.		Vacant Positions, directly leading to the Billing loss every month
38.	Incorrect allocation / apportionment of costs & revenue	Incorrect allocation / apportionment of costs, e.g. Transport, Facility, Administration costs etc and Credit / Debit notes
39.		Revenue and costs belonging to one single service unit, have been allocated to different cost/profit centres
40.		Manipulation/deliberate distribution of revenue/profits across project locations/segments/accounting period to show desired state of affairs
41.	Onsite deployment costs	Unable to leverage offshorability due to: 1. highest level of data security needs to be maintained 2. Nature of work requires physical presence of the employees at onsite 3. Customer mandated physical presence of the employees at onsite
42.	Travel & Transport Costs	Project team's travel to customer site due to escalations
43.		Local transport cost optimization not done